

Auf dem Weg zur intelligenten Mobilität

**Kurzfassung zum TA-SWISS Bericht «Das vernetzte Fahrzeug.
Verkehrstelematik für Strasse und Schiene»** ▶

Sur le chemin d'une mobilité intelligente

**Résumé du rapport TA-SWISS «Le véhicule en réseau.
Télématique des transports par route et par rail»** ▶

Sulla strada verso la mobilità intelligente

**Sintesi del rapporto TA-SWISS «Il veicolo in rete.
Telematica dei trasporti su strada e ferrovia»** ▶

On the road to intelligent mobility

**Abstract of the TA-SWISS report «The Networked Vehicle.
Transport Telematics for Road and Rail»** ▶

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TA-SWISS Das Zentrum für Technologiefolgen- Abschätzung

Neue Technologien bieten oftmals entscheidende Verbesserungen für die Lebensqualität. Zugleich bergen sie mitunter aber auch neuartige Risiken, deren Folgen sich nicht immer von vornherein absehen lassen. Das Zentrum für Technologiefolgen-Abschätzung untersucht die **Chancen und Risiken** neuer technologischer Entwicklungen in den Bereichen «Biotechnologie und Medizin», «Informationsgesellschaft» und «Mobile Gesellschaft». Seine **Studien** richten sich sowohl an die Entscheidungstragenden in Politik und Wirtschaft als auch an die breite Öffentlichkeit. Ausserdem fördert TA-SWISS den Informations- und Meinungsaustausch zwischen Fachleuten aus Wissenschaft, Wirtschaft, Politik und der breiten Bevölkerung durch **Mitwirkungsverfahren** (zum Beispiel PubliForen und publifocus).

Das Zentrum für Technologiefolgen-Abschätzung ist dem Schweizerischen Wissenschafts- und Technologierat angegliedert. Der SWTR berät den Bundesrat in wissenschafts- und technologiepolitischen Belangen.

TA-SWISS Le Centre d'évaluation des choix technologiques

Souvent susceptibles d'avoir une influence décisive sur la qualité de vie des gens, les nouvelles technologies peuvent en même temps comporter des risques latents qu'il est parfois difficile de percevoir d'emblée. Le Centre d'évaluation des choix technologiques s'intéresse aux **avantages et aux inconvénients** potentiels de celles qui surgissent et se développent dans le domaine des sciences du vivant et santé, de la société de l'information et de la mobilité. Ses **études** s'adressent tant aux décideurs du monde politique et économique qu'à l'opinion publique. Il s'attache, en outre, à favoriser par des **méthodes dites participatives**, telles que les PubliForums et publifocus, l'échange d'informations et d'opinions entre les spécialistes du monde scientifique, économique et politique et la population.

Le Centre d'évaluation des choix technologiques est rattaché au Conseil suisse de la science et de la technologie, qui a pour mission de faire des recommandations au Conseil fédéral en matière de politique scientifique et technologique.

TA-SWISS Il Centro per la valutazione delle scelte tecnologiche

Spesso le nuove tecnologie migliorano sensibilmente la qualità della nostra vita. Contemporaneamente, però, possono anche nascondere nuovi rischi, le cui conseguenze non sono sempre prevedibili. Il Centro per la valutazione delle scelte tecnologiche esamina le **opportunità e i rischi** dei nuovi sviluppi tecnologici nei settori scienze della vita e della salute, società dell'informazione e mobilità. I suoi **studi** si rivolgono sia ai responsabili della politica e dell'economia, sia al pubblico. Inoltre, TA-SWISS favorisce lo scambio di informazioni e di opinioni tra esperti della scienza, dell'economia e della politica e la popolazione attraverso **processi partecipativi** (ad esempio i PubliForum e i publifocus). Il Centro per la valutazione delle scelte tecnologiche è annesso al Consiglio svizzero della scienza e della tecnologia, che consiglia il Consiglio federale in materia di politica scientifica e tecnologica.

TA-SWISS The Centre for Technology Assessment

New technology often leads to decisive improvements in the quality of our lives. At the same time, however, it involves new types of risks whose consequences are not always predictable. The Centre for Technology Assessment examines the potential **advantages and risks** of new technological developments in the fields of life sciences and health, information society and mobility. The **studies** carried out by the Centre are aimed at the decisionmaking bodies in politics and the economy, as well as at the general public. In addition, TA-SWISS promotes the exchange of information and opinions between specialists in science, economics and politics and the public at large through **participatory processes**, e.g. PubliForums and publifocus.

The Centre for Technology Assessment is attached to the Swiss Science and Technology Council, which advises the Federal Council on scientific and technological issues.

On the road to intelligent mobility

Abstract of the TA-SWISS report «The Networked Vehicle. Transport Telematics for Road and Rail»

Central Zürich (Photo: Lucienne Rey)

Transport telematics actually has the hidden potential to revolutionise traffic movements in general.

Will «networked vehicles» mean falling traffic volumes?

When informatics and telecommunications merge into one, we talk of telematics. There are a number of areas of our everyday lives in which telematics are used, and one of these is transport. Transport telematics can do little to stem the avalanche of metal that hurtles through the main transport trunks every day. But it could help to overcome bottlenecks on road and rail more effectively than previously and to reduce the number of road deaths.

Nobody gave any thought to the dog. Including the driver of the pick-up that was moving into the lane heading for the town centre in Wankdorf. Then suddenly this mottled brown mongrel shoots out onto the highway, and a split second later the dark green four-wheel drive ploughed into the back of the IVECO pick-up: the emergency stop was too sudden, the distance between the vehicles too small. Fortunately, the only damage was to the metalwork, and even the puppy scurried away unharmed. But within minutes, there was absolute chaos: cars standing on the Wankdorf gyratory, blocking the exits off the motorway and back onto the town's streets, and the number 9 tram was cut off from the terminal loop at the terminus.

Then the «Wankdorf» incident control programme starts up in the Central Bern traffic management centre. Scarcely have the road surveillance system's cameras registered that the traffic on the Wankdorf gyratory has ground to a halt than the motorway exits, Papiermühlestrasse and Mingerstrasse start to turn red on the general map on the centre's large screen. The disruption on tramline number 9 will be displayed on the BernMobil operating control system terminal. But it's no problem for the three employees on duty: the traffic management programme runs automatically, according to the particular scenario. First of all the Wankdorf motorway exit is cordoned off. Cellular radio signals transmit the appropriate data directly into the navigation systems of the vehicles that are approaching the trouble spot, in time for an alternative route to be recommended to drivers. Information boards at the nearby exits for Neufeld, Schönbühl and Ostring warn motorists that there's no way through the Wankdorf gyratory. And those travelling on the main road from Worblaufen or Ittigen will be directed via Tiefenaustrasse or via Ostermundigen to the centre.

Nor are all those people standing at stops on tramline number 9 kept in the dark for very long: the neon writing on the passenger information board explains about the accident to those waiting and recommends that

they take the Wyler bus and travel into the northern part of town; extra buses will shortly be provided by the traffic management centre. People from outside the town can ring the centre on their mobile phone and have a general map of the district linked up to their mobile display. And assuming that half an hour after this fictitious traffic accident in the year 2012 the whistle blew in the Wankdorf stadium for the start of the Champions' League semi-final, and the fans were hurrying in their droves to support the Young Boys home team, yet another refinement of the telematic crisis management system would come into play: most of the football fans who were trying to get to Wankdorf would have «CombiTickets» that as well as giving them admission to the stadium also covered the use of public transport. If any of them had ordered their tickets on their mobile, they would receive an SMS with information about how they could best reach the stadium.

Pie in the sky? The future has already begun – the decision to hold a planning competition to redesign the Wankdorf intersection into a gyratory system was taken in the autumn of 2002. And the fact that in the medium term there will be a modern traffic management centre to ensure the well-orchestrated interaction of public and private transport might hardly seem any more utopian than the idea of the crisis-ridden Young Boys one day making it to the Champions League.

In the next few years, telematics will be offering us innovations that will make vehicles more efficient, more comfortable and safer. But the novelty of transport telematics is certainly not limited to so-called motorised individual transport – to the cars that we need

for the daily journey to and from work, for shopping or other errands. Transport telematics actually has the hidden potential to revolutionise traffic movements in general on rail and road, in the air and on the seas, by forming the different types of vehicle into nodes in an information network. However, the TA-SWISS report «The Networked Vehicle», on which the present abstract is based, limits its observations to road and rail transport.

Concerns about data protection will give rise to much discussion about the employment of transport telematics.

The three application fields for transport telematics

Information about the road network and traffic situation help to **distribute** and to **meter** the volume of traffic better: if you know early enough that there is a tailback blocking your route, you look for a diversion. The dynamic navigation systems that are already available today incorporate not just the necessary basic information about topography and the road network, but can constantly update their data by radio, so that they are also aware of short-term problems such as tailbacks or diversions. Telematics can, however, do more than simply influence the flow of traffic passively. So a control system could involve levying a user charge on roads where through traffic is particularly heavy in order to divert the flow of traffic. Transport telematics can be used in this case to calculate and to invoice the charges. Such interventions are loathed by all those people who are afraid that private transport will become ever more expensive. There is a lively debate among transport planners about «road pricing», something that is already in use in other countries.

Employing telematics means that private and public vehicles will be better **networked** with and among each other, and this will also play a part in coping effectively with the traffic flow. It is already possible on the internet to call up travel schedules and prices, national ones for the rail network as well as those of the innumerable regional and urban transport operators, to enable passengers to plan their optimum route. Thanks to cordless applications, travel planning information can now even be received on your mobile phone.

For the not-too-distant future, experts are doing painstaking work on «door-to-door route planners»: people who enjoy travel should one day be able to enter their starting point and destination, right down to the actual house number, on the internet, and receive a recommendation for the means of transport that will get them to their destination quickest and most easily – giving precise journey times, of course. Finally, trials are being carried out with chip-card tickets: with these, the passenger can be registered as soon as he or she gets into one form of transport and then leaves that to change to another. In principle this will make it easy to combine different forms of transport carriers such as hire cars, buses and trains with each other.

And not least, transport telematics can be used to help make **transport safer**. There are, for example, discussions taking place about automatic speed controls; if a car exceeds the permitted speed, a warning tone will sound. Once again, these are sensors that measure the free space in front of a vehicle's nose, and they are the basis for systems that should prevent collisions.

The networked Vehicle (Photo: www.h-h-auto.de)

Areas of contention ahead

Wherever telematics are employed to enhance the comfort of transport users, there is rarely any opposition. There is, however, some controversy about applications that are seen as excessive controls, or as state intervention in individual freedom of movement. In any event, concerns about data protection will give rise to much discussion about the employment of transport telematics – but there are certain telematic applications that enable journeys by individual transport users to be totally monitored. There is also a potential conflict in those areas where it is a question of the basic status and role of transport telematics.

Against this background, it would seem that there is an urgent need for an early priming of the social debate about transport telematics: in 2001 the Swiss Federal Department of Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications presented a strategy paper which assigned transport telematics a central role in putting into effect the Swiss government's transport policy targets. In the subsequent consultation among political parties and other interested organisations, however, it became evident that there is by no means universal approval of the principles set out in the report entitled «Road Transport Telematics: Guidelines for Switzerland in the year 2010». Data on the technical possibilities of transport telematics and about the organisational prerequisites will be absolutely essential to give the public examination of this technology a properly detailed basis, and to prevent it becoming mired in polemics and hardened positions.

In any event, concerns about data protection will give rise to much discussion about the employment of transport telematics.

There are many ways out of traffic chaos

If everyone uses the same roads at the same time, there's bound to be overcrowding. Transport telematics can exert a directing influence here, by distributing and metering traffic flows.

In your car, in a truck or on the railway: transport telematics has potential applications everywhere. The following sections give some information about the benefit that the various different transport carriers could derive from the latest developments in telematics, and what crunch issues there are still to be overcome.

Travel purposefully, with better information

In their search for unknown continents, early seafarers steered by the stars. Today, people steering their way through streams of traffic have more prosaic tools at their disposal. The **navigation systems** currently in use obtain their data from satellites and guide car drivers to their destination with a computer-generated voice, or by displaying details on the screen.

Telematic route-finders help to guide the flow of traffic as smoothly as possible. By recommending a selected route – known as «**routing**» – they help individual drivers to avoid losing their way in unknown surroundings and save them having to sit in traffic jams. Ultimately, everyone benefits from greater efficiency in traffic movements.

By the end of 2001, there were an estimated 3 million vehicles on Europe's roads equipped with a navigation system. And because the costs of telematic directional aids are still falling, they could soon be standard equipment in cars. Whether the advantages of these systems will continue to have any marked effect if they are used in greater numbers is, however, debatable: if a tailback on a trunk road is to be avoided, the capacity of the secondary road network has to be correspondingly large, since the more navigation systems there are in circulation, the greater the danger becomes of an overreaction in looking for alternative routes. The tailback would then simply be transferred from the motorway to the main road. And this could well harm many more people, in a residential district for instance, than it would on the freeway.

These fatal 'shift' effects can be avoided if the routes of individual vehicles were worked out by a central system. To do so, however, it would be necessary for the individual drivers to report to the centre and indicate where they wanted to go and when they wanted to get there. The system would then coordinate the routes of all vehicles with each other, to prevent overloading the traffic routes. Such systems as yet exist only in the fantasies of transport planners, and are a long way from becoming reality.

Apart from the navigation systems, there are other possibilities for enabling car and truck drivers to receive traffic information. Using variable text displays, transport users can receive information, for example about how full multi-storey car parks are, so that they don't have to chase around looking for

Deceptive safety

Like sea travel in the past, modern transport is also dependent on accurate directional aids. This is even true for the special case of military «cargoes» – for instance, in the deployment of cruise missiles. It was the military that played a part in the development of navigation systems that rely on the GPS (Global Positioning System) standard. In 1981, the US Department of Defense was involved in the development of a satellite-based location system to steer guided weapons better. In 1989, Blaupunkt introduced the first production-ready GPS navigation system for cars.

The satellites are used here as reference points, to determine a given location in space precisely. It involves measuring the time it takes for the signals from at least three satellites to reach the GPS receiver. Because the positions of the satellites are known exactly, the receiver is able to calculate its own location from the signal delay.

The rest of the world is allowed to use the United States' GPS system free of charge. But this is not an entirely selfless concession. The aim of the US military is to use it to ensure that they control the navigation data, and in an emergency – i.e. in a war or if there is a terrorist threat – are able to disrupt or switch off the system, making it difficult for an enemy to get its bearings. In order to free itself from this technological dependence, the EU is now investing massively in its own navigation system, called Galileo. Equipped with more accurate atomic clocks, and tailored to European specifications, the European competitor should deliver more precise data than the US model.

The hope that these technically highly sophisticated location systems will guarantee spatial orientation nevertheless remains a false one. The satellite signals are weak and can be interfered with at little cost. And under common conditions of everyday use, such as in very built-up urban areas, where the satellite is hidden from the direct line of sight, the result is often mis-positionings which can easily amount to several hundred metres. Seen in this light, there could even in the future be incidents such as the one in December 1998, when a driver, trusting blindly in his navigation system, drove his car into the River Havel in Caputh (Potsdam).

spaces. Variable text displays are also in use on motorways, e.g. as an element of **traffic control systems**. Here, sensors, video cameras or induction loops in the road surface can determine a variety of data, such as traffic density and weather situation. These data are collected centrally and evaluated, and the results entered into the electronic display boards, where the recommendations appear – mainly in the form of speed restrictions, but possibly also to warn of additional dangers such as tailbacks and ice, or to suggest using a less congested alternative route. Thanks to 'guiding' measures like these, traffic will ultimately flow more smoothly, and the risk of pile-ups and the probability of tailbacks will diminish.

In the longer term, however, variable text displays will increasingly become less important in directing traffic; there is already an apparent trend for data to be transmitted directly to the vehicles. This could, not least, reduce the new traffic 'blindness', because there would no longer be a need for the forest of screens on the roadside.

Metering through the wallet and at the traffic lights

Supply and demand control what happens in the economy: if a commodity becomes scarce, its price will increase. This principle can also be applied to road traffic for instance, by charging a **user fee** for certain sections of road. This toll, or as the transport experts call it «road pricing», could be flexibly structured, according to the time of day, and coordinated with demand: at peak times it would cost more to travel on that section of road, and less when traffic volumes were below ave-

rage. This would make it possible to reduce rush hour traffic peaks.

Road pricing could, however, not just be used to spread traffic in terms of time, but also to guide it in terms of space. If, for example, it is only possible to travel on a particular section of road if a charge is paid, it is likely that vehicles will avoid that section by switching to others. Consequently, user charges could be levied in places where the idea is to banish motorised vehicles – in residential areas, for instance, or in tourist locations – where only selected vehicles, such as taxis, ambulances, hotel suppliers might disturb strolling pedestrians. Finally, it would be conceivable to issue driving permits only for vehicles that meet certain conditions, for example cars whose drivers have already reserved and paid for a parking space in the area concerned. Transport telematics will be very useful in road pricing, recording what sections of road a particular vehicle has been driven on and passing a debit charge for the sections of road concerned.

In various foreign metropolises – e.g. in Oslo, Barcelona and Marseille – road pricing is already in use. Considerable attention is currently being focussed on the attempt in London to stem peak-hour traffic between 7 a.m. and 6.30 p.m.. Anyone who wishes to drive a car into central London on weekdays between the stipulated times will have to pay a £5 fee. Commuters will be able to obtain a daily permit in advance, or purchase a season ticket for a longer period. These may be paid for by telephone, on the internet, by post or in selected shops. It will also be possible to pay the charge later, although the charge is doubled if the delay is longer than 12 hours

Example of traffic control system (Photo: Lucienne Rey)

after the actual journey into central London. There is a special arrangement for residents. Although they will also have to make their own financial contribution to more open roads, they will only have to pay a special rate of 50 pence to drive into central London, even on weekdays.

For road pricing to be used effectively, and to keep administrative costs as low as possible, all vehicles will have to be fitted with a registration device. Particularly widely distributed are what are known as DSRC devices (Dedicated Short-Range Communication), which exchange data over a short distance

Transport telematics brings visions of individually tailored public transport within reach.

with radio terminals that are mounted on bridge-like metal constructions above the carriageway. These terminals send the requisite data about sections of road and travel times to the car. Using these data as a basis, the charge that is payable can finally be calculated. DSRC devices are widely distributed around the world, in Europe and in the USA, Japan, Australia and Central America. As there is nowhere in Switzerland (yet) that levies any usage-related road charges for private vehicles, in this country very few cars are actually fitted with an appropriate device. The situation with heavy transport is rather different: because of the capacity-linked levy on heavy goods vehicles (HVF), all Swiss trucks are fitted with DSRC-based vehicle devices that are connected via an interface with the tachograph.

Feelings are running high about the hiatus in cost-free personal freedom of movement that is the inevitable result of road pricing. It is also argued that it is difficult to find fair criteria for fixing rates. But there is one major advantage of usage-related charging that is indisputable: applied consistently, it increases the pressure to load vehicles better, and thus reduce the general volume of traffic. If the amount of the charge were to be determined by the type of vehicle, it could even affect the quality of the environment: why not give preference to cars that use fuel sparingly and emit few pollutants? A more positive effect of road pricing could also be that more people would be encouraged to switch to rail, bus and tram because of the increased cost of private transport.

Traffic can be **metered**, not just through the wallet, but also by traffic lights. A particular

type of traffic control system is being used successfully on the A1 motorway at Baden, to counteract the notorious Baregg tailback. If the control system registers that there are too many vehicles converging on the motorway, it holds cars back, allowing them to continue their journey according to the density of traffic (this is known as «ramp metering»). Of course, such measures restrict the ability of the individual to travel unimpeded. But experience has shown that control systems are accepted if they make sense to drivers.

Feelings are running high about the hiatus in cost-free personal freedom of movement.

If used in a strategically intelligent way, control and metering systems can effectively influence individual and heavy traffic on the road. Even public transport in urban agglomerations can benefit from telematic control systems: for example, it is possible to programme traffic signals in such a way that buses and trams are systematically given precedence over other transport users.

On the railways, however, there is little scope for using navigation or metering systems: the

sections to be travelled are fixed, and the individual trains are coordinated with each other. Improvements here could be achieved primarily by better networking of public transport with private transport, and by the fact that with telematic positioning and surveillance of trains frequencies could be increased without jeopardising safety.

A «drip-feed system» in the Gotthard tunnel

Following a serious traffic accident on 24 October 2001, which had been caused by two trucks passing, the Gotthard tunnel had to be closed for several months. It only reopened after precautions had been taken to reduce the risk of accidents. To begin with, a one-way rule was introduced for heavy traffic. Heavy trucks had to wait in a holding area until it was their turn to cross the mountain through the tunnel in groups. After a more efficient ventilation system had been installed in the tunnel, experts felt compelled to relax the strict traffic regime, and in October 2002 a new metering system was introduced. Trucks can once again pass, and are now «filtered» into the traffic, but at a safety distance of 150 metres. Two signal installations control the system – at a rhythm that depends on the traffic mix. If more vehicles are travelling than this «drip-feed system» is able to cope with, the heavy traffic is temporarily directed onto the holding area. This is actually the main weak point of traffic metering systems: if the capacity of the tailback area is inadequate, the space fills up behind the areas where the trucks are held. At the Gotthard tunnel, however, the installation has proved its worth with average traffic volumes, when there are about 3,500 lorries to be fed through daily: it meets safety standards just as it does the desire to make (relatively) swift progress. And trucks that are transporting particularly sensitive freight can apply for a special permit, allowing them to by-pass the preceding metering points and go directly to the light signal installations.

Metering system at the Gotthard tunnel (Photo: Alex Buschor, aPix, Zürich)

Vehicles as nodes in an information network

If you want to do a job efficiently, you need the right tools. So why should this principle not have any relevance to transport? With transport telematics the different transport carriers could be networked with each other in such a way that use could be made of their respective strengths.

If you want to be successful in this globalised society, you have to be independent, mobile and flexible. Mobility is a diktat of the busy age we live in. It is reflected in the convoys of cars that stream into commercial centres early every morning, carrying people to their place of work. In very rare cases, every seat in the car that is used for the daily commute to work is occupied. Often there are no more than two passengers in the car, and frequently it is just the driver. It is passenger transport that offers the greatest scope for the use of transport telematics.

Travel together, not alone

Transport telematics makes it possible, thanks to mobile data transfer, to announce transport requirements at short notice and to investigate suitable opportunities for car sharing. At the various **car-sharing centres** that have been set up all over Europe since the late 1990s, the internet and mobile phone help to bring drivers and people willing to car share into contact with each other. The car-sharing services that exist today are organised in the form of a forum; without compulsion, they help the potential car sharer to find the telephone number or e-mail address of a

possible driver. But there are also conceivable forms where the shared journey would be organised by a central office: driver and car sharers would give their details to the administrative office, which would also arrange the collection of moneys. The personal safety risk would then be reduced; although driver and passengers could preserve their anonymity in any personal contact, it would be possible, if the need arose, to obtain personal details through the central office. At present, such schemes are still proving unworkable because of the legal situation: if someone carries a passenger, and receives recompense for doing so, even if this is only in the form of sharing petrol costs, he or she is regarded as a professional chauffeur, and requires a licence. Seen from this point of view, the car-sharing services that already exist are operating in a legal grey area.

Car-sharing centres are used not least by young people, who are accustomed to getting information from the internet, do not yet have a car of their own and are put off by the high price of a rail ticket. There is a particularly strong demand for, and supply of, journeys between larger towns and cities. But trials are also currently under way in regional transport systems to organise private transport more efficiently.

A ticket for the ideal vehicle mix

The diversity of their tariff structures is still preventing the various regional public transport networks from growing together. Most urban regions are served by their own transport operator, and the different tariff systems are very difficult to coordinate. Even on the

national railway network, these regional operators that have been developed separately are not easy to link up. The obstacles are primarily organisational, political and legal in nature. At the technical level, solutions are already available.

There are, for instance, already **electronic tickets** in circulation – tickets similar to credit cards, fitted with a chip. They are recorded by special sensors as soon as the ticket holder enters a vehicle, which makes queuing at the ticket office no longer necessary. And, thanks to the tracking systems in the on-board computer, it can be ascertained which sections have already been travelled and which vehicle is being used. The monthly account covers all journeys that have been made on the various different means of transport that are connected to the composite system. It would even be conceivable to expand the system and also to invoice the charges for facilities such as ski lifts, indoor swimming pools or museums using the electronic ticket.

This brings visions of individually tailored public transport within reach: to travel to the next metropolis early in the morning, the passenger would be best served by the railway. Within the city, he could move around by tram and bus, without having to stand for ages at the ticket machine trying to work out how much he has to pay for a particular section. And if, in the evening, he wants to reach some isolated place in the surrounding countryside, he could obtain a car from the fleet of pool cars at the railway station. In this case, transport experts talk about what they call the **«intermodal route planner»**: before starting his journey, our traveller would

have entered on the internet where he wanted to go, and at what time. The route planner program would then have connected the different transport carriers to the appropriate plan for this specific mobility need. The invoice would be issued at the end of the month, and the bill would cover all journeys and services that had been used under the combined mobility scheme.

Electronic tickets are currently being tested in various pilot projects. In the Dresden conurbation, for instance, «Intermobil», the lead project of the German research initiative «sustainable mobility in cities» it should show how worthwhile flexible pricing, contact-free data transmission systems and a varied range of products are proving with public passenger transport, park and ride and hire cars (car sharing). Switzerland too has conducted comparable, wide-ranging pilot schemes: over 1,800 people in the Geneva and Basle agglomerations tested the «Easyride» system. Technically, the pilot project was a success. Nevertheless, it was discontinued in the spring of 2002. Apart from funding problems, one of the main decisive factors were concerns about data protection, because the monthly account can only be issued when the data have been stored for a correspondingly long period. This makes it possible, in principle, to record movement profiles of everyone using Easyride. This in turn is hardly consistent with the concern to preserve the private sphere of the individual.

«Carlos» on target

Since mid-April 2002 strange pillars have been standing on the roadside in the Burgdorf region (Canton Bern): they are about three metres high, topped with an illuminated display, and equipped underneath with an interactive screen («touchscreen»), which is used to input orders. The tall metal steles have been erected as part of the «Carlos» pilot scheme. Anyone wishing to use Carlos takes a ticket from the pillar for two francs and enters where they want to travel to on the «touchscreen». The name of the desired destination appears on the illuminated display, and drivers who are making for the same destination and read the corresponding notice on the display can stop and allow their passenger to get in. The driver keeps the ticket; when he has collected ten of them, he receives a 'Reka cheque' travel voucher for ten francs. The other half of the travel revenue is ploughed back into the project.

So in principle, Carlos is similar to conventional hitchhiking, but without the risks. A video system monitors all eleven stops, so that there is a measure of control over who has got into whose car. In addition, women can indicate that they only want to be picked up by another woman. And, if anyone has to wait too long for a car share, they have the possibility of calling a taxi via the telephone link on the pillar; the ticket they have taken is deducted from the taxi fare. The «Carlos» pilot scheme is due to last for three years. In the first six months, passenger numbers have been low, with a monthly average of 260 car sharers; there was all the more interest from transport experts from Switzerland and other countries.

Fewer empty journeys thanks to optimal fleet management

It is not just people that move around; goods do too. Transport telematics has become firmly established in the goods transport sector. It is employed in fleet management, to ensure that fleets of heavy trucks are optimally loaded and to avoid empty journeys.

Transport telematics can also be used to ascertain the present location of a specific cargo. What is known as **consignment tracking** is already widespread; roughly half of the transport vehicles in Europe are equipped with the necessary terminals and computer programs. It is now also increasingly possible to call up the relevant data on the internet, so that clients can track their cargo's journey on their screens. These tracking systems make it highly unlikely that a valuable cargo will get lost. It is also possible to inform consignees in good time when they can expect to receive their shipment.

Finally, transport telematics can also be used in goods transport to set up so-called **transport chains** in combined transport using truck and rail. Using a wireless information link to a central point, a time and place for transloading can be arranged at short notice. And if «piggy-back» transport should even more closely integrate the transport of goods by road and rail, transport telematics will also have a part to play.

Transport telematics applications that interfere in the driving process and virtually «disable» the driver would, however, require a fundamental change in our perception of the role a man or woman has to play at the wheel of a car.

For even greater road safety

Measured by the number of kilometres covered, driving a car is becoming an increasingly safe occupation. Nevertheless, some 600 people lose their lives every year on the roads in Switzerland, and roughly ten times as many suffer serious injuries in traffic accidents. Transport telematics could help further to improve road safety.

«VISION ZERO» – in future, no-one should suffer fatal or serious injury on the roads. That is the ambitious goal that the federal government has committed itself to in its current road safety policy (Vesipo). In their «Bases for a federal road traffic safety policy», experts from the Swiss Advisory Centre for Accident Prevention (bfu) have defined a series of measures for improving road safety. The paradigm on which the deliberations are based assumes that human failure can never be completely eliminated. Accordingly, technical measures that assist and take some of the strain from vehicle drivers, or even, in extreme cases protect them (and other road users) from themselves, are very important.

Guardian angel included

Excessive speed remains the crucial risk factor for traffic. The **speed limits** that are today indicated by signals supply information only at specific points; and if drivers fail to see them or disregard them, then they generally have nothing to fear in terms of consequences – unless of course they are caught by a police control. However, it might be possible to use a speed restriction transmitted continuously to vehicles via a mobile radio service, to warn drivers if they are exceeding the speed limit. More drastic designs are even looking at the possibility of speed limiters built into the engine that will cause the car to brake as soon as it tries to exceed the permitted speed. Such a technical «disabling» of the driver would, however, require a fundamental change in our perception of the role a man or woman has to play at the wheel of a car.

Another potential danger lies in the driver's state of health. It has long been known that we are better behind the wheel if we are well rested; and also that alcohol or drugs in the bloodstream impair our perception and ability to react. There is already equipment available that should prevent drivers from getting into dangerous situations. **Sensors** have been developed that analyse the breath of the driver and make it impossible to start the engine if the readings indicate the consumption of alcohol. Also under discussion are cameras that monitor the driver's eyes; as soon as the automatic picture evaluation system picks up signs of overtiredness, the system sets off a warning tone. Whether such constant control of a driver would be politically possible to implement, however, is questionable. And systems that actively

intervene in the driving process and curtail the driver's control, could come up against even stronger opposition.

Telematic surveillance systems could win more supporters if they were used to **control** dangerous **loads** in transit. In this case it could make sense to notify irregularities in the condition of a load not just to the truck driver, but also to a central point outside the vehicle.

Rail transport offers the best proof of reliability

The fact that today trains are able to leave a station on the same track at intervals of two to three minutes is due in no small measure to telematic safety technology. And further increases are conceivable: the possibility of introducing speed-dependent flexible intervals between trains, instead of setting fixed intervals between trains is being considered. Precise positioning and accurate speed measurements would each play a key part in this. Trains would then be able to follow each other more closely, without having to compromise on safety.

Another possibility for rail transport is the greater use of sensors that can detect obstacles ahead of the train and trigger an emergency braking system. Such safety systems are practicable on the track because the train will be travelling in a set direction. In the case of road transport, however, such **collision prevention** equipment is still coming up against limitations, as it is barely possible, technically, at present to integrate lateral evasive movements into the system.

Driver's cab of a ICE (Lucienne Rey)

Technically, there are many different ways in which the safety and efficiency of rail transport could be improved. But in a Europe that is growing together, frontiers are still having a restrictive effect: many installations are still being hampered by the fact that every country has introduced its own system, which

Opinions are divided, even among transport experts, about what transport telematics can actually achieve.

cannot be automatically connected to that of a neighbouring country. International harmonisation of safety technology and signalling systems is therefore an essential condition for achieving technical improvements. The European Rail Traffic Management System was the first step.

No «dead man» in the driver's cab

It is not just rail transport in general that is being constantly monitored, but also individual trains. As early as the 1930s, the safety control was introduced in Swiss trains: while the train was in motion, the engine driver kept the so-called «dead man's handle» constantly depressed; if the handle was lifted, an emergency braking system would be triggered within 100 metres. This precaution was to prevent a train racing out of control through the neighbourhood if the engine driver suddenly felt faint or fell ill. Over the years further safety systems were introduced. The ZUB train control system that was introduced on busy sections of line in the second half of the 1980s, for instance, checks whether a necessary reduction in speed is actually made within the required time. Before every journey and for each train arrangement the specific data for that arrangement (e.g. number of axles, weight of coaches and locomotive, brake percentage, etc.) have to be programmed into the system. Assisted by these data, and on the basis of information that has been transmitted to the ZUB by external sensors, the system works out the requisite deceleration and the ideal curve for the braking procedure. If the braking process deviates from the ideal, the ZUB system automatically applies the brakes.

Free travel or planned mobility?

Which strategies should be given preference in breaking down the bottlenecks on our roads, and what role should be given to public transport, depends on our answers to a series of fundamental questions. How we define quality of life, and how we regard our relations with society also colours our perceptions of which form our mobility should take.

The debate about transport telematics is characterised by two overriding disputes. One revolves around the technical and organisational feasibility of individual measures and around the influence that telematics can actually exert on traffic flow. The other is a fundamental one, and its central theme is the status of mobility compared to other basic concerns of society.

Opinions are divided, even among transport experts, about what transport telematics can actually achieve. Some see it as an effective instrument that could substantially increase the efficiency of the existing transport infrastructure. They take the view that this potential must be exhausted first, before we start to build new roads. Others, however, are convinced that the possibilities of transport telematics have been overestimated, and that we will therefore have to build new roads and set up new infrastructures immediately, in order to counter the imminent collapse of the transport system. In practical terms this dispute will probably be defused once it is established how well individual measures have performed in pilot projects.

How much mobility do people need?

Personal freedom of movement is one of our basic rights, and the car has long been held up as an emblem of individual self-realisation. For many people, freedom to travel where and when they wish in their own cars remains a vital element of personal quality of life. However, the voices of those who are expressing their vexation at the side effects of motorised mobility are becoming increasingly loud. They take exception to their living space being carved up by roads, the air being polluted by exhaust gases and the soil being sealed under layers of asphalt.

A healthy environment and less hustle and bustle in our everyday lives seem to many people to be a worthwhile goal, one that deserves to be given no less weight than the need for mobility. Against this background, it is debatable whether we should be looking for the means of dealing more effectively with traffic, while at the same time encouraging its further growth. Viewed in this light, transport telematics could meet with some reservations from people who are essentially sceptical about transport issues. Many telematics applications are also unlikely to be popular with those who are unwilling to have their personal striving for mobility curbed. And somewhere between the mobility refuseniks on the one hand and the champions of unimpeded freedom of movement on the other could be all those who take an objective view of transport telematics: as an instrument that offers possibilities of increasing the comfort, safety and efficiency of passenger and goods transport.

Collective interests have a hard time

If we give development a free rein, it is conceivable that many telematics applications will only be implemented singly – wherever they accommodate distinctive individual interests and do not impinge on the free space of the individual. Navigation systems, for example, might be broadly accepted: firstly, because every user expects some benefits from the growth of information, and secondly, because every user is free to follow the telematic recommendations, or not. Road pricing, by contrast, is having a difficult time; although in the view of the community it may be beneficial if user charges relieve the level of utilisation of cars, which means that traffic volumes would fall, and therefore that – depending on the arrangement – there would still be funds flowing into the public coffers. Notwithstanding that, for the individual the temptation to prevent any sort of drain on their own wallets is great.

Probably the most crucial factor in determining the future form of our mobility will be our willingness to subordinate our individual interests to matters that concern the population as a whole – whether, for example, we are prepared to plan our changes of location in advance, or whether we will persist in our right to choose where we go in our cars, spontaneously and at a moment's notice. The fundamental conflict, that individual and collective interests are mutually contradictory, is also reflected in the relationship between control, on the one hand, and preserving our personality on the other. Automatic speed controls, for instance, which increase road safety in general, are realisable only if certain

individual data can be obtained and – at least for the time required for evaluation – stored. Even systems that are aimed at interlinking individual transporters such as railways, urban transport and hire cars, and making it easier to use them with a monthly account, are dependent on the requisite data of all those who use this product being stored.

If the full potential of transport telematics is to be realised, we need an overall concept that is broadly supported politically and socially. This would have to take into account the technical, organisational, economic and legal aspects of using transport telematics. This is the only way to bring the different telematics applications into a balanced interaction, and thus to make full use of the benefits that derive from a flexibly used and optimally loaded transport infrastructure.

Ultimately, the question of what sort of mobility holds most promise for the future is one that will have to be dealt with as part of the social discourse.

Making a decision in the social debate

Only if the public as a whole are in favour of using transport telematics can its possibilities be utilised to the full. It is up to the policymakers and transport experts to involve the population in any discussions on the future of mobility.

The need for mobility is just one of the many concerns vying with each other within our society. The status it is accorded, and how it should be weighed against other qualities such as ecological sustainability cannot be ordained from above; it must be dealt with as part of the discourse with all parties concerned. The debate about which measures in terms of transport technology are appropriate, and under what conditions, will also depend on the answers to these basic questions.

The need for action is a real one

Irrespective of whether transport telematics is introduced as part of a comprehensive transport concept, or whether individual innovations achieve success by themselves, there is an evident need for action. There are already indications that certain groups are doing worse than others in utilising telematics services: the elderly or those whose sight is impaired are encountering problems when they ask for information or want to buy tickets at the terminal. In order for no-one to be systematically restricted in their mobility requirements, there is a need for targeted supplementary products for the disadvan-

taged and educational projects tailored for senior citizens, the disabled or other people who are put off by the notion of having to deal with modern technology.

If someone receives something in return for economising or for taking on some additional expense, it makes it easier for them to look favourably on unpopular measures. In this sense it would have to be considered whether those car drivers who load their cars better or are prepared to accept control sensors in their cars should be compensated financially. Existing car-sharing services are already on the quiet relying on the principle that travel costs will be shared among several people, and therefore cheaper for each of them, even if the current legal situation presents an obstacle to such arrangements. With regard to telematics systems such as sensors for automatic speed control or driver surveillance that increase general road safety, it would have to be considered whether occupants of cars fitted with the appropriate equipment should be rewarded by lower insurance premiums or other financial incentives.

Ultimately, however, the question of what sort of mobility holds most promise for the future is one that will have to be dealt with as part of the joint discourse. A solid knowledge base is an essential prerequisite for this: Information campaigns about pilot projects in which telematics measures are tested, but also training initiatives for people involved in local politics and municipal administration could help realistically to grasp the potential of transport telematics. And participative measures (e.g. round tables, PubliForum, publifocus), carried out by independent organisations, would guarantee that it will not be

only the experts that will be involved in designing the mobility of the future, but that all those who actually want to use their vehicles and are affected by traffic and transport issues will have their say too.

Die Studien des Zentrums für Technologiefolgen-Abschätzung TA-SWISS sollen möglichst sachliche, unabhängige und breit abgestützte Informationen zu den Chancen und Risiken neuer Technologien vermitteln. Deshalb werden sie in Absprache mit themenspezifisch zusammengesetzten Expertengruppen erarbeitet. Durch die Fachkompetenz ihrer Mitglieder decken diese so genannten **Begleitgruppen** eine breite Palette von Aspekten der untersuchten Thematik ab.

Le Centre d'évaluation des choix technologiques TA-SWISS se doit, dans toutes ses études sur les avantages et les risques potentiels des nouvelles technologies, de fournir des informations aussi factuelles, indépendantes et étayées que possible. Il y parvient en mettant chaque fois sur pied un **groupe d'accompagnement** composé d'experts choisis de manière à ce que leurs compétences respectives couvrent ensemble la plupart des aspects du sujet à traiter.

Gli studi del Centro per la valutazione delle scelte tecnologiche TA-SWISS devono fornire informazioni il più possibile fattuali, indipendenti e fondate sulle opportunità e sui rischi delle nuove tecnologie. Per questo motivo, sono realizzati in collaborazione con gruppi di esperti in materia. Grazie alla competenza dei loro membri, questi cosiddetti **gruppi d'accompagnamento** coprono un ampio ventaglio di aspetti della tematica esaminata.

Studies carried out by the Centre for Technology Assessment TA-SWISS are aimed at providing information concerning the advantages and risks of new types of technology which is as factual, independent and broad as possible. For this reason they are conducted in collaboration with groups of experts in the corresponding field(s). Thanks to the expertise of their members, these so-called **supervisory groups** cover a broad range of aspects of the issue in question.

Folgende Personen wirkten beim TA-SWISS Bericht «Das vernetzte Fahrzeug» in der **Begleitgruppe** mit:

Le groupe d'accompagnement du rapport TA-SWISS «Le véhicule en réseau» se composait des personnes suivantes:

Il gruppo d'accompagnamento del rapporto TA-SWISS «Il veicolo in rete» era composto dalle seguenti persone:

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